

METHODS

Mice

Conditional Pten^{fl/fl} mice were derived from the strain BRaf CA; Pten loxP; Tyr::CreER T2 (Jackson #013590). DBA1–C57BL/6 mice were maintained in the IN animal facility. All the animal procedures were approved by the regional Animal Care and Use Committee (2020/VSC/PEA/0235) and met the European (2013/63/UE) and Spanish regulations (RD 53/2013).

AAV2-injections into the retina and Optic Nerve Crush (ONC)

Adult (4–6-week-old) mice were anesthetized with isoflurane and received an intravitreal injection of a mixture of CreAAV2 and CNTFAAV2, followed 24 h later by an injection of c-mycAAV2. Two weeks later, optic nerve (ON) crush was performed in the injected eye. Briefly, mice were anesthetized by intraperitoneal injection of ketamine (100 mg/kg) and medetomidine (0.5 mg/kg), and received subcutaneous analgesia (buprenorphine). The ON was surgically exposed under an operating microscope and crushed 1 mm behind the eyeball for 5 sec using Dumont #5 inverted forceps. Human IL6AAV2 alone or together with Zic2AAV2 were injected intravitreally immediately after ONC. AAV2 CAG-EGFP and AAV2 CAG-EGFP-Cre were purchased to VVF (ETH Zürich). pAAV2 CNTF and pAAV2 c-myc constructs were generously donated by Zhigang He (Harvard University, US). pAAV2-Zic2 construct was produced by cloning human Zic2¹⁴ at EcoRI/BamHI sites of the pAAV2 plasmid. AAV2 particles encoding CNTF, AAV2 c-myc and Zic2 were produced at the Neurotropic Vectors Unit of the IN (<https://in.umh-csic.es/en/the-institute/services/neurotropic-vectors/>). AAV2 hyper-IL6 was prepared as described in¹⁷. The titer of the AAV2s ranged from 1.1-1.7 x 10E12 vg/ml. Animals recovered from anesthesia in individual cages and received a subcutaneous injection of atipamezole. All intravitreal injections were performed in a volume of 1.5 µl per virus. Two days before analysis, 1–2 µl of Alexa Fluor 555–labeled cholera toxin subunit B (CTB-555) was injected intravitreally into the ONC eye.

Immunofluorescence and RGC soma quantification in whole mount retinas

Retinas dissected from perfused mice were permeabilized and blocked using fetal bovine serum 1%, Gelatin 0.02% and Triton X-100 0.1% and incubated with Anti-GFP (chicken 1:1000, Aves Labs), anti-Pou4f1 (mouse, 1:300, Millipore), anti- β Catenin (mouse 1:500; BD Transduction Labs), anti-panEph (mouse, 1:300)¹⁸ and anti-Zic2 (rabbit, 1:500)¹⁹ overnight at 4°C. Alexa-Fluor secondary antibodies (1:400, Thermo Fisher) and Dapi were used. Retinas were mounted in flat-mount using Mowiol and coverslips were sealed with nail polish. Five or six equivalent areas were imaged per retina with a confocal microscope Olympus FV1200 with a 20x Oil objective, using constant laser settings and a z-interval of 5 micra. For colocalization and density measurements in the retina surface, somas were counted in 4-5 equivalent 0.1 mm²-squared areas per retina and the colocalization percentage or total density calculated. Colocalization percentages and density values were averaged first per retina and then per experimental group.

In utero electroporation and embryonic retinal explant cultures

Time-pregnant wild-type DBA1–C57BL/6 females at embryonic day 13.5 (E13.5) were anesthetized and in utero electroporation (IUE) was performed as previously described²⁰. pCAG-GFP and pCAG-Zic2 plasmids were injected into the embryonic eye at 0.5 μ g/ μ l and 1 μ g/ μ l, respectively. Retinal explants were prepared from electroporated embryos at E14.5 as previously described²¹ and cultured on glass-bottom dishes (MatTek) coated with 0.01% poly-L-lysine and 20 μ g/ml laminin and maintained in DMEM/F12 supplemented with B27, penicillin/streptomycin, and 0.4% methylcellulose.

Twenty-four hours after plating, explants were fixed in 4% paraformaldehyde (PFA), permeabilized with 0.025% Triton X-100, blocked in BSA, and incubated with anti-GFP (chicken, 1:1000; Aves Labs) overnight at 4 °C. Images were acquired using a Leica Thunder Imager inverted microscope equipped with a Leica DFC9000GTC camera. For axon length quantification, images were processed in Fiji, and axons were traced using NeuronJ. Axon lengths were averaged per experimental group.

Stripe assays with adult RGC explants

Stripes assays and adult RGC explants were prepared as previously described^{21,22}. FC recombinant protein (6 mg/ml) of, ephrinB1 or ephrinB2 (R&D system) were mixed with Alexa594-

conjugated anti-hFC antibody (Invitrogen) in HBSS for 30 min. Recombinant proteins were injected into matrices (90 mm width) placed on crystal coverslip pre-treated with poly-L-lysine, resulting in red-fluorescent stripes. After 30 min incubation at 37°C, coverslips were washed with HBSS, and matrices carefully removed. The coverslips were further coated with 6 mg/ml of FC protein mixed with anti-hFC (no fluorescent dye) for 30 min at 37°C, washed three times with HBSS and coated with 20 mg/ml of laminin for 2 h at 37°C. Retinal explants from adult *Pten^{fl/fl}* mice (P60) injected with *creAAV2 + GFPAAV2* or *creAAV2 + Zic2AAV2*, 2 weeks before the experiment, were cultured for 10 days-in-vitro (DiV) on the stripes and fixed with 4% PFA in PBS for 20 min at RT, washed and incubated with the mouse monoclonal anti-beta-III tubulin antibody (mouse 1:1000, Biolegend) and Alexa-488 anti-mouse secondary antibody. The total number of beta-III tubulin pixels on red or black stripes were quantified using Image J and an automatic stripe assay analysis²¹, calculated as repulsion index and represented as fold change in relation to Fc/Fc control stripes²³.

In situ hybridization in adult optic chiasms

E16.5 mouse embryos and P80 adult mice were intracardially perfused with 4% paraformaldehyde (PFA). The tissue was cryoprotected in 30% (w/v) sucrose in PBS and frozen in dry ice. Coronal and horizontal sections (35 µm) were obtained with a cryostat (Leica) and stored at -20° C until used. ISH was performed according to previously reported methods²⁴. To detect *Wnt5a* (NM_009524.4; 1143 to 2166 bp) and *ephrinB2* specific antisense riboprobes were used (gift of Ethan David, University of Rochester, NY, USA and S Williams, University of North Carolina, USA, respectively). Images were captured with a Leica DM2500 microscope equipped with a Leica DFC7000T camera.

iDISCO brain clearing and quantification of regenerating axons

Mice were anesthetized and transcardially perfused with PBS followed by 4% paraformaldehyde (PFA). Brains with the attached optic nerves (ONs) and eyes were carefully dissected and post-fixed in 4% PFA overnight at 4 °C. Tissue clearing was performed using the iDISCO protocol²⁵. Briefly, optic chiasm preparations with attached ONs were dehydrated in methanol and cleared with dichloromethane followed by benzyl ether. Samples were subsequently transferred to ethyl

cinnamate for refractive index matching and imaged on an Ultramicroscope II (LaVision BioTec) using a z-step of 1 μm . Optic chiasm z-stacks were 3D reconstructed, and CTB-labeled axons were manually traced using arivis Vision4D (Zeiss).

To quantify axon entry into the optic chiasm, individual CTB-labeled axons crossing an imaginary line drawn perpendicular to the ON at the chiasm entry point were counted in each experimental group. The midline was used as the reference boundary to classify axons as ipsilateral (remaining in the hemisphere of the injected ON and projecting toward the ipsilateral optic tract), contralateral (crossing the midline and extending into the opposite hemisphere), or retino-retinal (entering the contralateral ON). Axons that did not reach the midline, or that approached the midline but displayed ambiguous trajectories, were excluded from the analysis.

For the ipsilateral tract analysis, only ipsilateral axons extending >1 mm beyond the chiasm were included.

Statistical analysis

Male and female mice were randomly assigned to experimental groups. Statistical significance between two groups was assessed using an unpaired two-tailed Student's t-test. For comparisons involving more than two groups, one-way ANOVA was performed followed by Bonferroni's or Tukey's multiple-comparisons test, as indicated in the figure legends. Analyses and data visualization were conducted using RStudio and GraphPad Prism.

For stripe assays, data are presented as box-and-whisker plots, where the central line denotes the median, the box represents the interquartile range (25th–75th percentiles), and whiskers indicate the minimum and maximum values. Sample sizes (n) and exact P values are reported in the figure legends. A P value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant. Unless otherwise stated, data are shown as mean \pm s.e.m.